

**AFFIXATION AS A WAY OF WORD-FORMATION IN MODERN ENGLISH BASED
ON THE DATA OF THE OXFORD ENGLISH DICTIONARY UPDATES**

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Abstract: Статья посвящена проблемам аффиксального способа словообразования в современном английском языке. Рассматриваются продуктивные модели, продуктивные аффиксы на период с 2012 по 2014 год на материале дополнений к Большому Оксфордскому словарю, а также использование полученных данных при изучении иностранного языка

Keywords: аффиксация, продуктивность, суффикс, префикс, словообразовательная модель, Большой Оксфордский словарь

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the problems of affixation in Modern English. The article reviews productive models of affixation, productive affixes according to the OED online updates from 2012 till 2014, and using the data received in the educational process.

Keywords: affixation, productivity, suffix, prefix, model of word-formation Oxford English Dictionary.

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Introduction. Language is a reflection of human life. Modern society is in constant development: the rapid progress of science and technology, discoveries in the field of medicine. An important difference of the twenty-first century is a dense rooting of the Internet. All the changes that occur are recorded in the language, the vocabulary of which is updated daily with new lexical units. Annual vocabulary of English the language is replenished by an average of 800 lexical units [2].

One of the most authoritative and reliable sources is the Big Oxford Dictionary. Every year, additions containing new lexical units are published online on the site. Word formation is one of the ways to replenish the vocabulary of the English language. Affixation is defined by linguists as one of the most productive ways of forming new lexical units by adding word-forming affixes to various bases.

It is also necessary to designate the concept of productivity, which is defined by the term "word-formation activity", which implies the ability to word-forming means to form new lexical units.

The research material was 383 lexical units formed by the affixal method and selected from online supplements to the Large Oxford Dictionary for the period from 2012 to 2014 and published on the main website of the dictionary [6]. Despite the fact that affixation has been studied and is being studied by many linguists, due

to the productivity of this method of word formation, the affixal method is subject to further study. These affixal units are poorly studied, since they were recorded by the compilers of the dictionary relatively recently, which determines the relevance of the work. The purpose of the work a multidimensional analysis of fixed affixal lexical units has become possible.

As a result of the analysis, it was revealed that among 1,420 lexical units published in supplements to the Oxford Dictionary, 383 lexical units were formed using affixation, of which 133 lexical units were formed by prefix and 250 by suffixation [6].

It should be noted that this study did not take into account cases of using components such as aqua-, auto-, since, following such researchers as A.I. Smirnitsky [4], E.S. Kubryakova [3] and I.V. Arnold [1], units of this type were considered as semi-suffixes, since they carry a semantic load and can often act as independent units.

So, in 2012, among 392 new lexical units, it was recorded 69 lexical units formed using suffixation, and 6 lexical units formed using prefixation [6].

The most productive for 2012 was the suffix -y, participating for the formation of adjectives, – 7 lexical units, for example, LE aggregatory [6].

In 2013, 66 lexical units formed by suffixation and 18 prefixed neologisms were recorded. In total, 424 lexical units were recorded in the additions [6].

In 2013, the suffix with the highest productivity was the suffix of adjectives -ic (9 adjectives) and the suffix -ing of nouns (5 nouns), for example, utopic < utopia, discoupling < to discouple [6].

In 2014 , additions to the Great Oxford Dictionary included 604 lexical units from which suffixation was formed 110 new lexical units and by prefixing 115 lexical units [6].

The most productive in 2014 were suffixes -ed – 20 lexical units (for example, resented) and the suffix -ing involved in the formation of nouns (for example, firsting) [6].

For the period from 2012 to 2014, the un- prefix became the most productive, with the help of which 106 lexical units were formed (for example, unrefueled < refueled, unrefunded < refunded) [6].

Within the framework of this study, the most productive affixal word-formation models. The number of lexical units formed was taken as a classification feature, and productive models meant word-formation models with the largest number of new affixal units formed. As the analysis showed, for the period from 2012 by 2014, the model with the highest productivity was the V + -ed model = Adj [6].

Based on the model of this word - formation model, it was formed 26 lexical units [6] (for example, uncomfortable – to discomfort + -ed, demodulated – to demodulate + -ed).

In the course of this study, the compatibility of morphemes, namely affixes and roots and/or other affixes, was also investigated according to the etymological criterion. According to the data obtained, the group of words "root of foreign language occurrence + borrowed suffix" [5] has become the most extensive – 109 lexical units [6] (for example, scientific, creolist).

However, the model of interaction between the native English suffix and the root of a foreign language origin turned out to be no less productive [5] – 90 lexical units [6] (for example, walled, science).

There were also groups of interaction of native English suffixes and native English roots [5] (for example, blueward [6]) and the group "native English root + borrowed suffix" [5] (for example, kennedyesque [6]).

Among prefixed neologisms, due to the fact that the prefix of native English origin has become the most productive prefix un-, the most extensive group was the interaction of the native English prefix and the root of a foreign language origin [5] – 75 lexical units [6] (for example, unprotectable; there were other native prefixes, for example, under-: undercapitalization).

For the period from 2012 to 2014, based on data obtained by analyzing online additions to the Large Oxford Dictionary, it was found that out of 250 suffix units, 130 lexical units were formed using native English suffixes, and the most productive was the suffix -ed - 26 lexical units (for example, provided) [6].

Based on the data obtained during the study, it can be concluded that the interaction of morphemes of different etymologies in the word-formation act at the present stage of the development of the English language occurs quite freely, which indicates a high degree of assimilation of most affixal and root morphemes involved in the affixation process.

After analyzing the obtained affixal lexical units, we found that they can be conditionally divided into the following areas of use:

1. The sphere of science and medicine has become the most numerous group (for example, allinase, archistriatal [6]).
2. The sphere of use of "business and business communication" (for example, skiving, designee) [6].
3. The Internet sphere is interesting to consider. This group of vocabulary includes words related to the Internet space, online games (for example, firsting, Demogorgonian) [6].

Lexical units have also been recorded, which include areas such as law, art and print, healthy lifestyle, jargon and taboo vocabulary.

Thus, in the course of the study it was revealed that affixation is a productive way to replenish the vocabulary of English language at the present stage of its development. Speaking of special cases the affixal method of word formation, namely suffixation and prefixation, based on the data, it can be concluded that both of these methods are productive.

Online additions to the Large Oxford Dictionary are a valuable resource for any language researcher, including a beginner. It seems that the use of this Internet resource will be extremely useful to students in the course of lexicology of the English language.

Students can be offered a variety of search tasks, tasks aimed at studying the affixal method of word formation. Based on the data obtained, we have developed some tasks that can be used to study affixation.

As an example, consider one of the developed tasks. 1. Highlight the affixes of the following lexical units and explain their etymology: Satirizing (n.), ironizing (adj), creolist, scissored, unnecessarily, diasporic, scientological, individualness, eyewards, unmenacing, unrushed, discectomy, resounded, desalinization, diallelic. In this assignment, students need to perform a morphological word analysis, as well as use additional reference literature to determine the etymology of affixes. This task is designed for independent work of students. In the process of completing the task, students will get acquainted with affixes classified according to etymology, as well as analyze lexical units to highlight the affix of a word.

Summing up the research, it should be noted the productivity of both suffix and prefix word formation based on the material of additions to the Great Oxford Dictionary. Having considered word-formation models and having carried out morphological and etymological analysis of lexical units, a fairly free interaction of morphemes of various origins was noticed.

Statistical data have shown that the affixal way of word formation is not a characteristic feature of any particular sphere of use, but functions in various fields, such as science, medicine, people and people's relationships, law, business and market relations, etc. [6].

Based on the data obtained, it was also possible to establish, that the productivity of the affix and the productivity of the word-formation model are not always interrelated and may have different statistical indicators.

Conclusion. Thus, the study of the affixal method of word formation includes the accumulation of knowledge about the structure of the language being studied, the improvement of search skills, the development of oral and written literacy, and also contributes to language learning at a higher level.

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